

A Comparative Study between Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin Based on HbA1c Levels of Patients Diagnosed with Acute Coronary Syndrome and Heart Failure

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Abstract:

Objectives: The present study was to compare and evaluate the various risk factors for elevation of HbA1c level of patients treated with atorvastatin and rosuvastatin who will diagnosed with acute coronary syndrome and heart failure.

Methods: The study Subjects were divided based on patients taking Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin based on patient case notes, and doctor's notes. Among 100 patients, 54 patients were taken atorvastatin and 46 patients were taken rosuvastatin. The initial HbA1c levels were recorded, and the cases were followed up for a period of 4 to 6 months. Follow-up HbA1c levels were noted in data collection form.

Results: When we compared the mean baseline and follow-up HbA1c levels for Atorvastatin, there was a decrease of 1.171% from 8.412% to 7.241% among 54 patients. Similarly, when compared the mean baseline and follow-up HbA1c levels for Rosuvastatin, there was a slight increase of 0.146% from 8.576% to 8.722% among 46 patients.

Conclusions: HbA1c level is increased in older age as compared to younger age patients. And atorvastatin significantly decreases the HbA1c level from base line to follow up. While, HbA1c level is not significantly changed in rosuvastatin group patients. Aspirin and Vitamin B increases HbA1c level. While, Prednisolone and Vitamin C decreases the HbA1c level in patients with acute coronary syndrome and heart failure.

Key words: Acute Coronary Syndrome and Heart Failure, Atorvastatin, Rosuvastatin, HbA1c.

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Introduction

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide and statins remain the cornerstone of lipid-lowering therapy for the primary and secondary prevention of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD) events [1,2]. Statins have been shown to effectively lower low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL), which is a critical marker for the primary and secondary prevention of ASCVD [3,4]. The association between LDL levels and cardiovascular events and mortality is well established in the literature and relevant guidelines, whereby the classification of high-intensity statins is based on LDL reduction of $\geq 50\%$ to reduce risk of ASCVD [5,6]. Evidence has also shown that compared with moderate- or low-intensity statins, high-intensity statins decrease CVD risk more effectively [6–7]. Additionally, high-intensity statins are recommended by the 2013 American College of Cardiology (ACC)/American Heart Association

(AHA) Cholesterol Guideline, and 2018 ACC/AHA updated guideline for patients who are ≤ 75 years of age with clinical ASCVD (secondary prevention) regardless of LDL levels [5,8]. Despite this major shift in practice, many studies that evaluated the prescribing trends of statins in clinical settings found that less than half of the patients with ASCVD were prescribed high-intensity statins [9,10].

Statins are medications that inhibit the rate-limiting step of the conversion of HMG-CoA to mevalonate, which in turn reduces the synthesis of cholesterol. The reduction in hepatic cholesterol levels leads to an increase in the expression of LDL receptors in liver cells, which results in increased clearance of LDL particles from the blood. As a result, lowering plasma LDL-cholesterol by statins reduces the synthesis and increases the catabolism of apo B 100. It's worth noting that the mevalonate pathway generates products such as coenzyme

Q10, heme-A, and isoprenylated proteins, which play a significant role in cell biology and human physiology. Although the role of statins has been assumed to be widespread in areas such as inflammatory markers, nitric oxide (NO), polyunsaturated fatty acids, immunomodulation, neuroprotection, and cellular senescence [11].

Additionally, Statins produce isoprenoid metabolites that result in the inhibition of small GTP binding proteins (such as Ras, Rac, and RhoA). These proteins are responsible for various non-lipid-mediated activities, including anti-inflammatory, antithrombotic, and antioxidant effects [12]. Statins also increase nitric oxide (NO) production, improve endothelial dysfunction, and cause insulin resistance due to the inhibition of isoprenoid biosynthesis and down-regulation of C/EBP α production. Decreased synthesis of isoprenoids can lead to the downregulation of GLUT4 expression on adipocyte cells, which can decrease insulin-mediated cellular glucose uptake and lead to glucose intolerance. Another mechanism of Statins is an increase in the production of NO, which can induce cytokines causing β cell apoptosis [12].

Objectives

1. To compared HbA1c of patients treated with atorvastatin and rosuvastatin who will diagnosed with acute coronary syndrome and heart failure.
2. To evaluated the various risk factors for elevation of HbA1C level in patients of ACS and HF who will treated with atorvastatin and rosuvastatin.

Materials & Methods

The present study was conducted in Department of Pharmacology, with the collaboration of Department of Medicine and Biochemistry, in SKMCH, Bihar during a period from January 2023 to August 2023. Attendant of entire subjects will be signed an informed consent approved by institutional ethical committee, of SKMCH. Data will be collected with irrespective of age and sex by the use of random sampling methods.

Table 1: Comparison of Mean HbA1C % between base line to follow up of Non diabetic and diabetic patients.

HbA1c%	HbA1c base line		P-value	HbA1c follow up		P-value
Diabetic status	Non-diabetic	Diabetic		Non-diabetic	Diabetic	
	12	88		12	88	
Mean \pm Standard deviation	6.564 \pm 1.412	9.112 \pm 1.862	<0.0001	6.576 \pm 1.024	9.052 \pm 1.283	<0.0001

In the present study, when we compared the mean baseline and follow-up HbA1c levels for Atorvastatin, there was a decrease of 1.171% from 8.412% to 7.241% among 54 users.

A total of around 100 acute coronary syndrome and heart failure patients were enrolled in this study.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients who were treated with atorvastatin and rosuvastatin for at least 3 months.
- All hospitalized acute coronary syndrome patients with or without diabetes mellitus and all hospitalized heart failure patients with or without diabetes mellitus.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with altered LFT may alter the enzyme activity and pregnancy and lactating Women.

Procedure: This data was obtained from a preliminary diagnosis chart. This study that took place in the inpatient wards of a tertiary care hospital. Patients were chosen based on their diagnosis of ACS, HF, CAD, or IHD and their treatment with Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin.

The study Subjects were divided based on patients taking Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin based on patient case notes, and doctor's notes. Among 100 patients, 54 patients were taken atorvastatin and 46 patients were taken rosuvastatin. The initial HbA1c levels were recorded, and the cases were followed up for a period of 4 to 6 months. Follow-up HbA1c levels were noted in data collection form.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed with the help of SPSS software. Mean \pm Standard deviations were observed. P-value was taken less than or equal to 0.05 for significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$).

Observations: All the patients who treated with Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin were included in the present study. The sample size totalled 100, with 62(55%) males and 38(45%) females. The population was categorized into four groups: 30-40 years old (5%), 41-50 years old (15%), 51-60 years old (22%), and over 61 years old (58%).

Based on Statistical data, for non-diabetic patients there was a Mean increase in HbA1c from 6.564 % to 6.576 \pm %, for Diabetic patients there was a mean decrease in HbA1c from 9.112% to 9.052%.

Table 2: Comparison of Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin based on HbA1C baseline and follow up.

Mean of HbA1c	Base line	Follow up	P-value
Atorvastatin	8.412±1.756	7.241±1.864	0.001
Rosuvastatin	8.576±2.187	8.722±1.943	0.735

When compared the mean baseline and follow-up HbA1c levels for Rosuvastatin, there was a slight increase of 0.146% from 8.576% to 8.722% among 46 users.

Table 3: Comparison of Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin based on HbA1C baseline.

Mean of HbA1c	Atorvastatin (Base line)	Rosuvastatin (Baseline)	P-value
	8.412±1.756	8.576±2.187	0.678

When compared the mean HbA1C level between base line of atorvastatin and rosuvastatin. It was not significantly differences (p=0.678). while, mean between follow up of atorvastatin and rosuvastatin was significantly differences (p=0.0002).

Table 4: Comparison of Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin based on HbA1C follow up.

Mean of HbA1c	Atorvastatin (Follow up)	Rosuvastatin (Follow up)	P-value
	7.241±1.864	8.722±1.943	0.0002

In the present study, comparing different doses of Statins and HbA1C, for a 10mg dose, there was a decrease of HbA1c from 8.316% to 8.142%, for a 20 mg dose there was a decrease of HbA1c from 8.876% to 8.264%, for 40 mg dose there was a decrease from 8.654% to 8.285%. Based on the data Patients are categorized into with Hypothyroidism and without Hypothyroidism, we have 22 Hypothyroid patients and 78 non-hypothyroid patients, when we checked the HbA1c baseline and follow-up, in Hypothyroid patients there was a slight increase in HbA1c i.e., 0.2% and non- Hypothyroid patients it is decreasing in mean HbA1c% i.e., 0.42% decrease.

Based on the data, among 87 subjects, 3 patients used Aspirin and observed a 0.76% increase in HbA1c, 6 patients were treated with prednisolone and observed a 0.27% decrease in HbA1c, 3 patients were treated with Vit B and there is 0.2% increase in HbA1c, 1 patient was treated with Vit C, and observed 0.3% decrease in HbA1c.

Discussions`

Different types of statins may have different effects on the glucose metabolism [13,14]. In general, statins are classified according to their hydrophobicity into hydrophilic statins (pravastatin and rosuvastatin) and lipophilic statins (atorvastatin, cerivastatin, fluvastatin, lovastatin, pitavastatin, and simvastatin) which have different pharmacological properties [15,16]. Although the target of both types of statins is HMG-CoA reductase, the inhibitory mechanisms are distinct. Hydrophilic statins target the liver more efficiently because their uptake is carrier-mediated, while lipophilic statins passively diffuse through the hepatocellular membrane and also in extrahepatic tissues, thus showing reduced hepatoselectivity [16,17], which may explain their higher incidence of adverse effects. Exception to this is rosuvastatin,

which is a hydrophilic statin, but has a similar activity profile to lipophilic statins [18].

A previous studies have shown that statin treatment was associated with the increase of hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) and altered glycemic control [19]. A large retrospective and cohort study has shown that the use of high-potency statins, atorvastatin and rosuvastatin, may increase HbA1c levels in patients with or without diabetes [19]. Furthermore, a recent meta-analysis has showed that statin treatment was associated with increase of HbA1c in individuals with adequate or altered glycemic control [20]. Similar, a randomized and controlled study in patients with Type 2 diabetes conducted in Taiwan found that HbA1c was significantly increased after 3 months in patients receiving atorvastatin [21]. On the other hand, in a randomized study of non-diabetic patients, neither of high-potency statins investigated (atorvastatin and rosuvastatin) had a significant effect on HbA1c [22].

In the present study, there was significant decrease of mean of HbA1C from 8.412% to 7.241% in atorvastatin group patients (p=0.001). We also observed Dose-related changes in HbA1c, a previous study was done in 1049 diabetic patients and observed patients who received rosuvastatin 5 mg and atorvastatin 10 mg, there was no significant difference between the two groups in the effect of HbA1c during 12 months and after that period there was an increase, and for rosuvastatin 40 mg and atorvastatin 80 mg after 24 weeks there was a statistical increase in HbA1c%.

In our Study we observed for 10 mg dose of both Statins there was a decrease of HbA1c, for 20 mg dose there was a decrease of HbA1c, for 40 mg dose there was a decrease [23,24]. An intervention trial evaluating rosuvastatin (Jupiter) trial comparing 20 mg of rosuvastatin to a placebo, a statistically significant increase in physician-reported type 2 diabetes was noted (p=0.01). The

Controlled Rosuvastatin Multinational Study in Heart Failure (CORONA) study reported a nonsignificant risk of developing diabetes while taking rosuvastatin [24]. Our study stated that For Rosuvastatin there is a mean increase in HbA1c from 8.576% to 8.722% these results we found that Atorvastatin is safer when compared to Rosuvastatin in reducing HbA1c thereby reducing the risk of diabetes mellitus.

As a continuation of our study, we compared other cofactors like age, sex, and disease especially hypothyroidism, A previous study investigated the association between HbA1c levels and age in Taiwanese adults without a prior diagnosis of diabetes. In general, the HbA1c levels increased with aging and the levels of males were significantly larger than females, the HbA1c levels did not increase with age for the age group of 50-70 years in males [25].

In our study we found that in the 30-40 age group, there was a decrease in HbA1c from 8.79% to 6.86%, in the age group 41-50 there was a decrease in HbA1c from 8.98% to 7.89%, in the age group 51-60 there is an increase in HbA1c from 6.84% to 7.96%. So, we can say 30 to 50 there was a decrease in HbA1c and from age group 51 and above there was an increase in HbA1c. In both males and females, there is a decrease in HbA1c, we compared HbA1c with Gender, and we observed in Males and females there is a decrease in HbA1c. Diseases like Hypothyroidism which is related to endocrine glands also influence HbA1c, so, according to a previous study they have presented preliminary findings on, 40 long-term diabetic subjects, less than 70 years of age and under regular supervised medical management. They screened these patients, for vascular dysfunction using thermal imaging, to obtain risk scores for diabetes, hypertension, and dyslipidemia.

In the present study, we had 22 Hypothyroid patients and 78 Non-Hypothyroid patients, when we checked the HbA1c baseline and follow-up, in Hypothyroid patients there was a slight increase in HbA1c i.e., 0.2%, and in non-Hypothyroid-patients it is decreasing in mean HbA1c i.e., 0.42% decrease. Finally, we also did changes in HbA1c with drugs, according to a previous study High doses of antioxidant agents such as Vitamin C and E have been reported to lower the HbA1c by reducing the rate of glycation of hemoglobin, Chronic use of aspirin in large doses can lead to acetylation of hemoglobin, leading to falsely elevated HbA1c levels due to interference with some of the assays used.

Patients with anemia due to deficiency of iron and vitamin B12 have high HbA1c levels. This can be reversed with the administration of the deficient factor. In some cases, administration of iron and

vitamin B12 can lead to falsely lowered HbA1c due to the preponderance of young erythrocytes in circulation [25].

In the present study, we observed among 100 subjects, 3 patients used Aspirin and observed a 0.76% increase in HbA1c, 3 patients were treated with Vit B and there was a 0.2% increase in HbA1c, 1 patient was treated with Vit C and observed a 0.3% decrease in HbA1c .so, so there is an increase in HbA1c in patients who are using Aspirin and VIT B, but very less patients using these drugs we can ignore the data. In another study done in COPD patients who are diabetic and nondiabetic and who are treated with Prednisolone they found that there was a significant increase in HbA1c [26]. In our study. we found that 6 patients were treated with prednisolone, and observed a 0.27% decrease in HbA1c.

Sola et al. [27] revealed that statins can inhibit the synthesis of inflammatory cytokines and chemokines, improve autonomic function, and reverse myocardial remodeling. Also, statins might retard the progression of myocardial dysfunction by promoting plaque stabilization and reducing the progress of CAD. The use of atorvastatin in patients with non-ischemic heart failure improves EF and decreases the adverse LV remodeling [27].

Conclusions

The present study concluded that the HbA1c level is increased in older age as compared to younger age patients. And atorvastatin significantly decreases the HbA1c level from base line to follow up. While, HbA1c level is not significantly changed in rosuvastatin group patients. Aspirin and Vitamin B increase HbA1c level. While, Prednisolone and Vitamin C decreases the HbA1c level in patients with acute coronary syndrome and heart failure

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